

EMPOWER ADULT EDUCATORS TO SUPPORT DIGITAL SOCIAL INCLUSION

Cooperation partnerships in adult education

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Digital Inclusion To Improve People's Lives and Promote Sustainable Development

DIGIN Report III

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Digital Inclusion to Improve People's Lives and Promote Sustainable Development

WORKSHOP III

Instytut Badań i Innowacji w Edukacji – Poland
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Introduction

In an era of rapid technological advancements, digital inclusion has transcended from mere buzzwords to fundamental necessities impacting every facet of human life. It represents the democratisation of technology, ensuring equitable access and the ability to participate in the digital sphere actively. It, in turn, unlocks a treasure trove of opportunities for individuals and communities, empowering them to navigate the complexities of the modern world and chart a path towards a more sustainable future.

This paper, presented as part of the Empower Adult Educators to Support Digital Social Inclusion (DigIN) project, delves into the intricate relationship between digital inclusion, social well-being, and environmental sustainability. It aims to unpack the multi-pronged impact of digital technologies on various aspects of our lives, highlighting their potential to:

- **Bridge the Social Divide:** The digital divide, characterised by unequal access to technology and skills, exacerbates existing social inequalities. Digital inclusion efforts, however, can bridge this gap by providing individuals with the tools and knowledge necessary to engage with the digital world effectively. It opens doors to improved access to education, healthcare, employment opportunities, and social networks, fostering a more inclusive and equitable society.
- **Enhance Environmental Quality and Development:** Environmental sustainability hinges on fostering responsible resource management, mitigating climate change, and promoting green practices. Digital technologies play a crucial role in achieving these goals by:
 - **Enhancing Data-Driven Decision Making:** Real-time data collection and analysis facilitated by digital tools enable stakeholders to track environmental trends, identify areas requiring intervention, and optimise resource utilisation. It leads to informed decision-making, promoting sustainable practices at individual and systemic levels.

- Facilitating Green Innovation: Digital technologies fuel the development of innovative solutions for environmental challenges. Smart grids optimise energy distribution, precision agriculture minimises resource waste, and green building technologies promote energy efficiency. We can accelerate the transition towards a sustainable future by empowering individuals and organisations to adopt and contribute to these innovations.

However, the question remains: Can digitalisation lead to reduced industrial pollution? The answer lies in a nuanced approach that acknowledges technology's challenges and opportunities. While certain aspects of digitalisation, such as increased reliance on electronics manufacturing and data centres, can contribute to energy consumption and e-waste, several vital factors can mitigate these drawbacks:

- Environmental Investment: Prioritising investments in renewable energy sources, energy-efficient technologies, and sustainable infrastructure like recycling facilities is crucial. It ensures that the digital ecosystem operates on an environmental responsibility foundation.
- Green Innovation: Fostering research and development in clean tech, resource efficiency, and closed-loop manufacturing systems is essential. It minimises the environmental impact of digitalisation and paves the way for solutions that actively address existing pollution challenges.

The transformative power of digital inclusion extends beyond theoretical constructs. Cities like Kraków, Poland, demonstrate the tangible impact of technology in fostering sustainability. Through initiatives like the "Smart City Kraków" program, the city leverages digital solutions to:

- Reduce Energy Consumption: Smart meters and building management systems optimise energy usage in public buildings.
- Improve Air Quality: Real-time monitoring and data analysis inform targeted interventions to tackle air pollution.

- Promote Sustainable Transportation: Smart ticketing and bike-sharing programs encourage eco-friendly travel options.

Kraków's success story is a testament to the potential of digital inclusion to drive positive environmental change. Replicating and adapting such initiatives across different contexts requires concerted efforts from educators, policymakers, and communities.

Empowering Adult Educators: Key to Unlocking Potential

The DigIN project, with its focus on enhancing the capacity of adult educators, plays a pivotal role in this crucial endeavour. The project enables educators to effectively guide adult learners on their digital journeys by equipping them with the necessary digital skills and knowledge. It, in turn, empowers individuals to become active participants in the digital world, unlocking a world of possibilities for personal and professional growth while contributing to building a more sustainable future.

Moving Forward: A Collective Responsibility

Bridging the digital divide and harnessing the power of technology for social good and environmental sustainability is a joint responsibility. By fostering dialogue, collaboration, and investment in capacity building, we can create a future where everyone can thrive in a digital and sustainable world. This paper serves as a call to action, urging individuals, organisations, and policymakers to make digital inclusion a reality. Through collective action, we can unlock the vast potential of technology to build a more equitable, prosperous, and sustainable future for generations to come.

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DIGITAL SOCIAL INCLUSION AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

1. Introduction

The Republic of Türkiye, recognizing the transformative potential of digital technology and data, has strategically positioned itself for comprehensive digital social inclusion and environmental sustainability. The establishment of the Digital Transformation Office (DTO) and the commitment to a national digital government strategy underscore Türkiye's dedication to leveraging digital advancements. Moreover, the emphasis on technology as an enabler for understanding users' needs and addressing environmental concerns reinforces Türkiye's commitment to user-driven, inclusive, and proactive governance.

Digital inclusion is a transformative force that has the potential to revolutionize societies by bridging gaps, fostering equal opportunities, and contributing to sustainable development. The government's initiatives, including critical assessments of digital transformation programs, refinements in e-government services for inclusivity, and specific figures on renewable energy consumption, align seamlessly with a vision of an inclusive and sustainable digital future.

Integrating these strategic efforts into the existing framework provides a holistic approach to navigating the complexities of the digital age while fostering social inclusion and environmental resilience. This chapter explores the intricate relationship between digital social inclusion and environmental sustainability, with a focus on examples from Türkiye. The modernisation of Türkiye's digital landscape has empowered its citizens and paved the way for initiatives addressing pressing environmental concerns.

2. Methodology

The research process includes conducting in-depth desk research and synthesizing information from many sources to have a complete picture of the Turkish context. Primary

sources include official reports, academic publications, and market insights, whereas secondary sources are case studies, statistical data, and expert analyses.

3. Digital Social Inclusion Initiatives in Türkiye

In Türkiye, the integration of government-led efforts and private-sector involvement demonstrates a shared commitment to digital inclusiveness and environmental sustainability. This creative synergy highlights not only a shared goal for advancing widespread digital accessibility and equality but also the country's commitment to sustainable environmental practices. As public and private institutions collaborate, their efforts help to shape a forward-thinking and sustainable path for Türkiye's digital and environmental landscape.

Government Initiatives

Türkiye's commitment to digital social inclusion is exemplified through initiatives such as the "Digital Turkey" program. This multifaceted initiative aims to empower citizens across all demographics with essential digital skills. For instance, in collaboration with local municipalities, the government has set up Digital Literacy Centers in underserved areas. These centres offer training on computer literacy, internet usage, and digital security, ensuring that even those with limited access to resources can participate in the digital economy.

Another noteworthy government effort is the "Smart Village" project. Recognizing the urban-rural digital divide, this initiative focuses on enhancing connectivity and digital infrastructure in rural areas. Through the establishment of community technology hubs, residents gain access to online education, telemedicine services, and e-government platforms. This holistic approach ensures that digital inclusion extends beyond urban centres, promoting equitable opportunities for all citizens.

Private Sector Contributions

Leading corporations in Türkiye are actively engaging in initiatives that contribute to digital social inclusion. For instance, partnerships between tech giants and non-profit organizations have led to the development of affordable devices tailored for low-income individuals.

This collaborative effort not only addresses the issue of digital access but also includes comprehensive training programs to bridge the digital skills gap.

Moreover, corporate mentorship programs play a crucial role in nurturing talent from underrepresented communities. Tech companies organize workshops and mentorship sessions, fostering a supportive environment for individuals to enhance their digital skills and pursue careers in technology. These private sector initiatives align with the broader national agenda of creating a digitally literate and inclusive society.

In Türkiye, several leading corporations and tech companies have actively contributed to digital social inclusion initiatives.

Turkcell: Turkcell, one of Turkey's largest mobile operators, has been involved in various initiatives promoting digital inclusion. They have undertaken projects to increase digital literacy, especially in rural areas, and have worked on providing affordable connectivity solutions.

Vodafone Turkey: Vodafone Turkey has been active in promoting digital inclusion through its corporate social responsibility programs. These initiatives often focus on providing technology access and education to underserved communities.

Türk Telekom: As a major telecommunications company in Turkey, Türk Telekom has been involved in efforts to bridge the digital divide. They have undertaken projects to increase broadband access, particularly in rural areas, and have contributed to digital literacy programs.

Microsoft Turkey: Microsoft, being a global technology company, has engaged in partnerships and initiatives in Turkey to promote digital skills and education. Their efforts often include providing software, resources, and training to support digital inclusion projects.

IBM Turkey: IBM has historically been involved in projects aimed at fostering digital skills and innovation in Turkey. Their initiatives include collaborations with educational institutions and organizations to promote technology literacy.

Intel Turkey: Intel, a global technology leader, has been involved in initiatives to enhance digital education and access to technology. Their contributions include support for educational programs and technology infrastructure projects.

4. Environmental Sustainability Efforts: E-Government

Turkey's commitment to environmental sustainability is reflected in its innovative use of e-government services for environmental management. The Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate's online platforms enable real-time monitoring of air and water quality, waste management, and environmental impact assessments. This digital infrastructure not only enhances the efficiency of regulatory processes but also promotes transparency and public participation in environmental decision-making.

A notable example is the "Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Information System," an online platform where citizens can access information about ongoing environmental assessments, submit feedback, and participate in public consultations. This digital approach enhances the accessibility of environmental information, fostering a sense of environmental stewardship among the public.

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) in Türkiye

The Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) process is a critical component of environmental management and sustainable development. It involves evaluating the potential environmental effects of proposed projects before they are implemented. This ensures that decision-makers, stakeholders, and the public are informed about the potential environmental consequences of certain activities.

- **EIA Process in Türkiye:** In Turkey, the EIA process is regulated by the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate. Various projects, including industrial facilities, infrastructure projects, and energy developments, undergo an EIA process to assess and mitigate potential environmental impacts.
- **Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Information System:** The "Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Information System" is an online platform developed by the Turkish

government to enhance transparency and public engagement in the EIA process. This digital platform is designed to make information about ongoing environmental assessments easily accessible to the public.

- **Key Features:**

Accessibility of Information: The platform allows citizens to access detailed information about ongoing EIA processes. This information includes project descriptions, potential environmental impacts, and proposed mitigation measures.

Public Consultation: The system facilitates public participation by providing a mechanism for citizens to submit feedback and comments on ongoing EIA processes. This input can be crucial in ensuring that a diverse range of perspectives is considered in decision-making.

The platform provides information about public consultations related to specific projects. This allows interested individuals to participate in hearings, meetings, or discussions concerning the environmental impact of proposed projects.

By making EIA information readily available and providing opportunities for public input, the digital platform aims to foster a sense of environmental stewardship among the public. It empowers citizens to be actively involved in the decision-making process, promoting environmental awareness and responsible citizenship.

Green Technology Adoption

Türkiye's commitment to environmental sustainability is evident in its embrace of green technologies, particularly in the energy sector, where the country has made significant strides in adopting renewable energy sources. The "Renewable Energy Resource Zones" project, initiated and implemented by the Turkish government, plays a crucial role in this endeavour.

The project, part of the government's broader strategy to promote renewable energy sources and achieve sustainable development goals, involves identifying specific areas with high potential for harnessing renewable energy, such as solar and wind power. The government designates these zones to encourage and streamline the development of renewable energy

projects, making it easier for investors and developers to focus their efforts in areas with optimal conditions.

Implementation typically involves collaboration between government authorities, local communities, and private sector entities. The government plays a crucial role in providing regulatory frameworks, incentives, and support to ensure the success of such projects. By strategically planning and designating these zones, Turkey aims to boost its renewable energy capacity and reduce reliance on conventional energy sources, contributing to both environmental sustainability and energy security.

Smart city initiatives in major urban centres showcase the integration of digital solutions for sustainable urban living. From intelligent traffic management systems to energy-efficient public lighting, these initiatives aim to reduce environmental impact while enhancing the overall quality of life. The adoption of electric public transportation and the promotion of eco-friendly practices in urban planning further exemplify Turkey's dedication to green technology adoption.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings from Türkiye's experience in digital social inclusion and environmental sustainability underscore the effectiveness of collaborative efforts across government, private sector, and civil society. The multifaceted initiatives presented in this chapter showcase a holistic approach that considers the diverse needs of communities while addressing environmental challenges.

Türkiye's journey serves as a valuable case study for nations seeking to emulate a model of digital and environmental synergy. By intertwining digital social inclusion and environmental sustainability, Türkiye not only enhances the quality of life for its citizens but also contributes to the global imperative of sustainable development.

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DIGITAL SOCIAL INCLUSION AND ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY AND DEVELOPMENT

1. Context and relevance

Digital social inclusion has become imperative for sustainable development in the current digital era. The digital divide, limiting equitable access to digital technologies, exacerbates social inequalities and hinders progress in environmental matters. However, digital inclusion is a fundamental right and a powerful tool to enhance environmental quality and promote sustainable development.

Significance of Digital Social Inclusion

Digital social inclusion enables people to access information and knowledge about environmental issues, empowering them to make informed decisions and participate in collective action. For instance, digital platforms can facilitate access to environmental data, such as air or water quality, allowing communities to monitor their surroundings and take measures to protect them. Similarly, digital inclusion facilitates citizen participation in environmental decision-making processes. Digital technologies can create virtual spaces for debate and public consultation, ensuring greater transparency and accountability. Ultimately, digital inclusion equips communities with the necessary tools to defend their environmental rights and promote sustainable solutions. Communities can use digital technologies to organise, share information, and report environmental issues, driving positive changes in their surroundings.

Impact on environmental quality and development

The digitisation of environmental management allows better data collection and analysis, optimising efficiency and decision-making. Governments and environmental organisations can use sensors and digital platforms to gather real-time data on air quality, water,

deforestation, and other environmental indicators. This information can be used to identify risk areas, develop intervention strategies, and assess the impact of environmental policies. Digital inclusion also promotes the green economy. Digital technologies can be used to develop and adopt clean technologies, such as renewable energy, smart agriculture, or efficient water management. It can boost the creation of green jobs, stimulate innovation and competitiveness, and contribute to the transition to a more sustainable economy.

Challenges and opportunities

Despite its potential, digital social inclusion faces several challenges. The digital divide persists, with marginalised groups such as rural communities, women, and low-income individuals falling behind. A lack of digital skills limits people's ability to harness the opportunities offered by technology. Additionally, digital technologies' production, use, and disposal have an environmental impact that must be carefully considered. Investing in digital infrastructure, such as broadband and public access centres, is necessary to overcome these challenges. Developing digital literacy programs that provide people with the skills needed to use digital technologies effectively is also essential. Finally, the technology sector must adopt sustainable practices to minimise environmental impact. Therefore, digital social inclusion is a critical environmental quality and development factor. Addressing challenges and seizing the opportunities presented by technology is crucial to building a more sustainable and inclusive future for all. Investing in digital inclusion is not only an investment in the present but also in the future of our planet.

2. Bidirectional Relationship between Digital Social Inclusion and Environmental Quality

The relationship between digital social inclusion and environmental quality is bidirectional. Digital inclusion can contribute to environmental improvement; conversely, a better environment can facilitate digital inclusion.

Specific Examples:

- **Environmental Monitoring:** Digital technologies can monitor air quality, water, deforestation, and other environmental indicators. Communities can utilise this information to take measures to protect their surroundings.
- **Smart Agriculture:** Digital technologies can be used to optimise resource usage in agriculture, such as water, fertilisers, and pesticides. It can help reduce agriculture's environmental footprint and improve soil and water quality.
- **Renewable Energies:** Digital technologies can manage the production and distribution of renewable energy, such as solar and wind energy. It can help reduce dependence on fossil fuels and greenhouse gas emissions.
- **Access to Information:** Digital inclusion facilitates access to information on environmental issues, such as climate change, pollution, and conservation. It can help individuals make more informed decisions about their lifestyle and its environmental impact.
- **Citizen Participation:** Digital technologies can promote citizen participation in environmental decision-making. Digital platforms can facilitate communication between communities, authorities, and environmental organisations.

Benefits for Communities:

- **Health Improvement:** A better environment can enhance the health of communities, reducing the incidence of respiratory, cardiovascular, and pollution-related diseases.
- **Food Security:** A more sustainable environment can improve food security, ensuring access to clean water, fresh food, and natural resources.
- **Economic Opportunities:** Digital inclusion and the green economy can generate new economic opportunities for communities, especially in smart agriculture, renewable energies, and ecotourism.

- **Social Empowerment:** Participation in environmental management can empower communities, enabling them to make decisions about their future and improve their quality of life.

3. Towards a Sustainable and Inclusive Future through Digital Social Inclusion and Environmental Quality

We live in a crucial era where the environmental crisis and the digital divide pose two monumental challenges for humanity. However, amid this complexity, a unique opportunity arises for harnessing digital social inclusion to forge a more sustainable and inclusive future.

An Ambitious Plan for the Future

Implementing an ambitious and multifaceted action plan focusing on three fundamental pillars is required to achieve this goal.

1. Closing the Digital Divide

To ensure equitable access to digital opportunities, it is essential to invest in infrastructure that ensures everyone has access to high-speed internet, regardless of location or socio-economic condition. Additionally, implementing digital literacy programs will be essential so everyone can maximise the opportunities technology offers. Promoting the development of affordable digital devices is crucial, ensuring that technology is accessible to all.

2. Empowering Citizen Participation

Facilitating access to precise and up-to-date environmental information through digital platforms is essential to empower communities. Creating virtual participation spaces will allow communities to contribute to environmental decisions and express their opinions. Furthermore, implementing transparency and accountability will ensure more efficient and

fair environmental management, with active citizen participation in assessment and monitoring processes.

3. Promoting the Adoption of Clean Technologies

Encouraging public and private investment in clean technologies through fiscal and financial incentives is essential for a sustainable future. Training communities and businesses in the efficient use of clean technologies are vital, as well as facilitating the transfer of these technologies between countries and regions, especially towards developing nations.

A Joint Effort

This ambitious action plan does not solely rely on governments but demands a collective effort from all social actors. Governments, businesses, civil society organisations, and citizens must collaborate to implement policies, adopt responsible practices, develop programs, and embrace sustainable lifestyles.

A Personal Commitment

Individually, we take responsibility for educating ourselves about environmental issues and technological solutions, participating in volunteering activities related to environmental protection, using digital technologies responsibly and sustainably, and supporting organisations working for digital social inclusion and environmental quality.

The path towards a more sustainable and inclusive future may be challenging, but the potential of digital social inclusion to improve environmental quality is a powerful tool that should not be overlooked. It is time to act together to build a future where technology is an instrument for humanity's well-being and the planet's protection.

We can build a better future where technology and nature coexist harmoniously, social inclusion is a reality, and environmental quality is a fundamental right for all.

4. Sustainable and participatory transformation: a plan with clear objectives and defined strategies

Strategic planning is essential when tackling significant challenges. In this context, reducing the digital divide and strengthening citizen participation are critical goals for building a sustainable future. This essay proposes an action plan with specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound objectives, focusing on three critical areas: reducing the digital divide, strengthening citizen participation, and promoting clean technologies.

Specific Objectives and Strategies:

1. Reducing the Digital Divide:

- **Objective 1.1:** Increase broadband internet access to 90% of the population within five years.
 - *Strategy:* Invest in digital infrastructure and digital literacy programs to ensure widespread access.
- **Objective 1.2:** Reduce the gender digital divide by 50% within three years.
 - *Strategy:* Implement specific policies and programs to address gender disparities in digital access and literacy.
- **Objective 1.3:** Provide digital literacy to 70% of the population within two years.
 - *Strategy:* Develop training programs tailored to different population groups, ensuring most acquire digital skills.

2. Strengthening Citizen Participation:

- **Objective 2.1:** Implement a digital platform for access to environmental information within one year.
 - *Strategy:* Develop digital platforms to facilitate access to clear and updated environmental information.
- **Objective 2.2:** Create virtual spaces for citizen participation in environmental decision-making within two years.
 - *Strategy:* Establish online spaces for citizens to express opinions and contribute to environmental decisions.
- **Objective 2.3:** Increase citizen participation in environmental management by 30% within three years.
 - *Strategy:* Implement transparency mechanisms, accountability, and awareness campaigns to promote active participation.

3. Promoting the Adoption of Clean Technologies:

- **Objective 3.1:** Increase investment in renewable energy by 20% annually.
 - *Strategy:* Offer fiscal and financial incentives to stimulate public and private investment in clean technologies.
- **Objective 3.2:** Develop training programs for using clean technologies within one year.
 - *Strategy:* Implement training programs for communities and businesses, promoting the efficient use of clean technologies.
- **Objective 3.3:** Reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 10% within five years.
 - *Strategy:* Establish regulations and policies encouraging emission reduction and promoting clean technologies.

Resources for Implementation:

The critical resources for implementing this plan include public and private funding, collaboration with various sectors, volunteerism, and active community participation. Detailed strategies encompass awareness campaigns, digital platform development, training programs, and incentive implementation.

1. Public and Private Funding:

- Collaboration between the public and private sectors is crucial. It includes government budget allocations, private investment funds, and public-private partnerships supporting specific projects.

2. Multisectoral Collaboration:

- Collaboration extends beyond funding to coordination between diverse sectors. Active involvement of the private sector, civil society, and academia in plan design and implementation ensures varied perspectives and experiences.

3. Volunteerism and Community Participation

- Community engagement is essential. Establishing volunteer programs enables active participation from individuals committed to the cause. Encouraging civil society participation in environmental decision-making creates a sense of ownership and shared responsibility.

Monitoring Indicators and Timeline

Measuring progress and goal fulfilment is essential for long-term success. Monitoring indicators provide a clear view of the plan's impact and effectiveness. Additionally, a timeline outlines short, medium, and long-term actions.

Monitoring Indicators

1. Access to Internet and Digital Technologies:

- Percentage of the population with broadband internet access.

- Number of digital devices accessible to different population segments.

2. Citizen Participation:

- Number of people participating in environmental management activities.
- Quantity of opinions expressed in virtual citizen participation spaces.

3. Adoption of Clean Technologies:

- Several renewable energy projects have been implemented.
- Percentage reduction in greenhouse gas emissions.

Timeline

- **Short Term (1-2 years):**
 - Implement awareness campaigns.
 - Develop primary digital platforms.
 - Initiate pilot training programs.
- **Medium Term (3-5 years):**
 - Expand coverage of internet access and digital literacy programs.
 - Consolidate and improve existing digital platforms.
 - Expand training programs nationally.
- **Long Term (5+ years):**
 - Significantly reduce the digital divide.
 - Achieve high citizen participation in environmental management.
 - Promote widespread adoption of clean technologies.

This approach is an adaptable starting point tailored to the specific needs of each community. Its success depends on the commitment and collaboration of governments, businesses, civil society organisations, and the general citizenry. By addressing the digital divide, strengthening

citizen participation, and promoting the adoption of clean technologies, we can pave the way for a more inclusive, participatory, and sustainable future.

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DIGITAL SOCIAL INCLUSION AND ACTIVE PARTICIPATION

1. Introduction

Social Engagement taking part in the community is emphasized in the Netherlands society. The Dutch populace is highly engaged in society. 'Participating' can mean different things to different people however understanding that actively engaging in activities outside the home – physically or virtually. Active participation like volunteering, sports, work, and education in each life stage different levels of involvement variables.

2. Seniors' social engagement

The older generation has opportunities and challenges in keeping up social involvement and connections as societies in the digital age continue to change. Seniors' general well-being is greatly influenced by their social involvement and participation, which also greatly improves their mental health and sense of community. The idea of "digital inclusion" has gained popularity recently as a potent means of bridging generational divides, encouraging connectedness, and improving the quality of life for the elderly. Seniors' social engagement is not just a question of leisure; it is a critical factor in determining their overall physical and mental well-being. Social interaction has been connected to enhanced mental health, better cognitive performance, and a lower incidence of depression. But as people get older, several things can make it harder for them to engage in typical social settings, like geographical distance, physical restrictions, and shifting social networks.

The endeavour to guarantee that every person, irrespective of age or background, has equitable access to and proficiency with digital technology is known as digital inclusion. Although there has been worry about the digital divide, attempts to close this gap are gathering steam, especially as more people realize the potential advantages for senior citizens.

Seniors can have fun and engage in interactive experiences using digital entertainment and gaming platforms. Seniors have a wealth of interesting things to do with their free time, ranging from brain-twisting puzzle games to virtual cultural events.

The key to opening up a world of opportunities for seniors and improving their general well-being and social involvement is digital inclusion. It is crucial to make sure that seniors are not left behind as society adopts the digital era. We can build a culture where elders not only adjust to the digital environment but flourish in it, enjoying "digital sparkling" and feeling more connected to the outside world by promoting digital inclusion.

3. Digital inclusion as a spark

In a time when technology is king, digital inclusion offers a revolutionary way to encourage older people to participate in social activities. As computers, tablets, and smartphones become more and more common, the digital world opens up a world of possibilities for interacting with people, getting information, and taking part in online communities.

Despite geographical differences, digital platforms help senior citizens maintain relationships with friends and family. Social media sites, messaging applications, and video conversations provide a virtual environment for exchanging experiences and preserving deep connections. A multitude of information about hobbies, health, and local activities may be found online. Older adults can use online courses to seek lifelong learning, remain up to date on healthcare news, and stay informed about local events.

With the use of digital platforms, senior-focused online communities may be created that cater to their interests and requirements. Social cohesion is promoted by these communities because they provide a feeling of community and shared experiences.

The utilization of digital inclusion enables senior citizens to have quicker and more comfortable access to telehealth services. For people who live in rural locations or have restricted mobility, this is especially important.

Digital inclusion for the elderly has obstacles despite the potential advantages, such as technology limitations, low digital literacy, and worries about online safety. To ensure that senior citizens feel comfortable and secure while navigating the digital world, community activities, workshops, and initiatives can be very helpful in overcoming these obstacles.

According to the model (figure 1 based on Holgersson, J., Söderström, E., Rose, J. (2019), actors engage in social practices that are facilitated by online technology through digital inclusion (eInclusion), which is influenced by significant contextual circumstances. Evaluation is a useful tool for tracking the results of the initiatives on digital inclusion. The main players are the senior citizens themselves, governmental organizations that coordinate digital services and support inclusion initiatives, nonprofits like Assist the Elderly and telecom and tech companies that supply digital services and Internet infrastructure. Researchers look into a variety of digital inclusion initiatives, such as communication through social media, tablets, and smartphones use of e-commerce and online entertainment by senior citizens, community involvement, and eGovernment services.

Figure 1. The eInclusion for the elderly model (Holgerson, J., Söderström, E., Rose, J., 2019)

Kuoppamäki, S., Hänninen, R., Taipale, S. (2022) emphasized that “To engage actively with digital technologies, older adults may benefit considerably from social and technical support from other people who share their everyday lives and lifeworld, within or outside the same household”. From an ethical standpoint, our research also presents concerns about the relationship between digital and social inclusion. Most the European countries advocate for greater digital inclusion for everybody by enhancing the usability of digital public services as a means of preventing social and digital exclusion. While there's no denying that digital

inclusion makes older folks feel more socially included, others may choose to maintain their social connections in person rather than through digital means.

Sustainability and social engagement are related ideas that help build a society that is more fair, inclusive, and environmentally conscientious.

The goal of community-based sustainability projects is to instill eco-friendly behaviors in nearby communities. Community gardens, recycling initiatives, and community-benefitting energy-saving projects are a few examples of this.

By combining community engagement with sustainability efforts, communities can foster a sense of shared responsibility for both social and environmental well-being. For example, a community garden not only promotes sustainable agriculture but also serves as a social hub for residents.

Combining sustainability with social involvement creates a potent mix that can result in long-lasting, beneficial change. Building a sustainable and inclusive future requires a holistic strategy that takes social and environmental well-being into account, whether at the community level, inside businesses, through education, or on digital platforms.

4. Conclusion

For senior citizens, digital inclusion can completely change their social environment by providing them with new opportunities for involvement, connection, and personal fulfilment. To fully realize the potential of technology, communities, legislators, and technology suppliers must collaborate to make sure that digital tools are easily available, easy to use, and specifically designed to meet the requirements of the elderly. By doing this, we may build a community that is inclusive and global, where age no longer serves as a barrier but rather presents a chance for ongoing social interaction and participation.

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DIGITAL SOCIAL INCLUSION AND ECOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS: KRAKÓW – SMART CITY

1. Introduction

The idea of smart cities is part of a broader development concept adopted by the European Union, that of so-called smart growth. About cities, it is understood as the development that supports those development resources with which the city can compete for new investments and residents.

2. Methodology

The research process used a case study analysis, which is one of the qualitative research methods. The main purpose of this method is to illustrate a certain case in the best possible way. It provides an in-depth analysis of a specific phenomenon. The case study is one of the qualitative research methods. The main purpose of this method is to best illustrate a certain, as the name says, "case". It provides an in-depth analysis of a specific phenomenon. It includes a detailed analysis of the case, goals, objectives, assumptions, motives, and actions.

3. Findings

As an intelligent and modern metropolis, Krakow aims to become a strong centre of new activity for Poland, Europe and the world in 2030.

Drawing 1. Kraków -smart city 2030

Source: Resolution No. XCIV/2449/18 of the Krakow City Council of 7 February 2018 on the adoption of the document "Development Strategy of Krakow. This is where I want to live. Kraków 2030."

A smart economy should be based on modern services, industry and the R&D sector, have developed business spaces that generate the development of creative industries, exhibit innovation, labour market flexibility and effective cooperation between science and business.

The initiators of change in the city should be the citizens, who, with their high qualifications and competencies, creativity and ability to interact, with the support of ICT, can strive for a continuous improvement of the quality of life in the city.

A smart city gives its inhabitants a friendly place to live, in particular by providing wide access to public services (including online services), high-quality education, health care and care for the elderly, and modern technical and social infrastructure, by striving for a high level of

security, by providing an attractive cultural and leisure offer, and by caring for the environment and green spaces.

The city should have an integrated and safe transport system, using solutions from the information and communication technology sector. With modern infrastructure, the city should create an efficient network of high-speed links connecting all its resources.

A smart city optimises energy consumption, carries out measures to protect and adapt to climate change, measures to reduce emissions of pollutants into the environment, and the management of the city's resources is based on the principle of sustainable development, using infrastructure based on modern technology.

Smart management is understood as public management in which competence, public participation in decision-making, transparency of operation and high quality and accessibility of public services play an important role. It requires the creation of an integrated city management system, taking into account the participation of all city users in the realisation of smart city goals and effective cooperation between the public and private sectors.

To realise the vision of a Smart City, the City Manager has developed a kind of Portfolio Strategy "Kraków Smart -City". The strategy sets out a timeframe for achieving all the goals set for the year 2030. The vision was to, among other things, create a tool in the form of a Project Portfolio "Kraków Smart - --City" to improve the quality of life in the city by taking advantage of the benefits of digitisation and building a sustainable and inclusive city with a society involved in the development of the city.

As a result of this vision, the Mayor of the City of Kraków, by Order No. 655/2023 of 13 March 2023, appointed the Project Portfolio Board for the implementation of the project portfolio entitled "Kraków-Smart City", which, as a specialised task force, decides on the projects included in the Portfolio leading to the development and implementation of initiatives improving the quality of life in Kraków by the Smart City principles.

The projects included in the Portfolio are carried out by the process "Project, *Programme and Portfolio Management*" and the process "*Strategic City Development and Monitoring of*

Strategic Goal Achievement", in the scope adjusted to each project separately in connection with the budget and the multi-annual financial forecast¹.

The referenced Portfolio aims to aggregate smart city projects and manage them in an integrated manner. The objectives of the Portfolio, as well as the project portfolio itself, is a tool for the implementation of the Kraków Development Strategy 2030.

Table 1. Strategic Objectives of the Kraków Development Strategy 2030

Strategic Objectives of the SRK 2030	Operational objectives of the SRK 2030
I. Kraków - as an open and harmonious metropolis of international importance in the spheres of innovation, science, economy and culture	I.1 Kraków - a node in the network of Polish, European and world metropolises I.2 Coordinated use of the potential of the Krakow Metropolitan Area
II. Kraków - a city developing a knowledge-based economy	II.1 Cooperation between science, business and government II.2 Supporting business innovation II.3 An education system adapted to the needs of a knowledge-based economy
III. Kraków - a modern, creative metropolis benefiting from its cultural potential	III.1 Kraków as a European Capital of Culture III.2 High cultural competence of the inhabitants
IV. Kraków - a liveable city	VI.1 Accessible, high-quality public space for all IV.2 Revitalised urban areas IV.3 Environmental Sustainability

¹ Ordinance No. 655/2023 of the Mayor of the City of Kraków of 13 March 2023 on the appointment of the Portfolio Council and Portfolio Manager for the implementation of the Portfolio entitled "Kraków -Smart City"..

	<p>IV.4 A resident-friendly, efficient and environmentally friendly transport system</p> <p>IV.5 High level of security in Krakow</p> <p>IV.6 Widespread implementation of the concept of healthy and active living</p>
V. Strong self-governing community of Krakow's inhabitants	<p>V.1 High level of social participation of residents</p> <p>V.2 Strong community-based organisations (NGOs) sector</p> <p>V.3 Social cohesion</p>
VI. Kraków - a modernly managed metropolis	<p>VI.1 Friendly and efficient administration</p> <p>VI.2 High-quality of strategic city management</p>

Source: Resolution No. XCIV/2449/18 of the Krakow City Council of 7 February 2018 on the adoption of the document "Development Strategy of Krakow. This is where I want to live. Kraków 2030."

A strategic priority for Krakow is to achieve the status of a modern managed metropolis in 2030.

To fulfil the vision of a smart city set for itself, Krakow started building pilot systems for data integration and analysis in 2023 -advanced data processing systems and big data systems using machine learning and artificial intelligence. The years 2024-2025 saw pilots of smart data-driven solutions -smart video surveillance, and smart parking. Pilot solutions especially aimed at residents will be the mKraków mobile application, open data, and service portals.

Gaining experience in implementing smart city solutions, Krakow is taking part in the international Smart EPC project (<https://zdmk.krakow.pl/>). As part of it, in addition to replacing lighting with LEDs, it will test the implementation of Smart City elements that can be used for vehicle charging. In a survey, residents selected locations where such stations could appear. As part of the Smart EPC project, Krakow is testing the use of LED lanterns for vehicle

charging. These are not very large devices and can improve the service of electric vehicles. To familiarise residents with such a solution, a demonstration of such an e-charger took place in the field on 13 April (on Borsucza Street).

A questionnaire was then made available (between 13 April and 15 May 2023), in which locations could be indicated for such devices, allowing charging, both in terms of shorter, longer and full charging cycles. Attention was paid to ensuring that the locations typed were near a public road -for cars, in the area of a pavement or cycle path -for scooters -generally on land owned by the municipality. Smart EPC is a project co-funded by the HORIZON 2020 programme, which is being implemented with the cooperation of several European cities. Its coordinator is Croatia and its partners are Spain, France, Poland and Belgium. Krakow is a partner in the project and at the same time acts as a pilot, as a city that has committed to replacing street lighting with energy-efficient lighting based on the standards developed within the framework. The main objective of the project is to be able to replace street lighting by EPC standards -an ESCO company will be responsible for this, and will be remunerated for the electricity savings achieved. By participating in this project, Krakow will test the implementation of Smart City elements using its street lighting infrastructure.

The project plans to test the following activities:

- Implementation of external light sensors for dynamic luminaire dimming/brightening about lighting from external sources, e.g. illuminated advertising, building displays,
- implementation of additional services such as e-chargers,
- communication with the luminaires via the monitoring and control system,
- implementation of a dynamic luminaire control and monitoring system to enable dynamic luminaire control, collection of breakdown data,
- implementation of additional services in the form of data transmission infrastructure (under consideration).

An example of a local project on the Smart City strategy for Krakow and the Krakow Metropolitan Area is "SMART_KOM. Kraków in the network of smart cities" carried out by the Kraków Technology Park, the Małopolskie Voivodeship and the City of Kraków. In the report summarising the first stage of the project, the concept of "smart mobility" occupies an important place among smart city solutions. In the face of dynamically developing metropolitan areas, organising transport services for the population is a real challenge for

local authorities. In the example of Krakow, which is struggling with the problem of smog and traffic jams in the city, a smart rail transport system is particularly welcome. Reducing the volume of car traffic in the city will certainly contribute to reducing the scale of exhaust fumes produced by vehicles and the dust caused by the wear and tear of car parts such as brake pads or discs. This approach fits in above all with the idea of low-carbon, which is one of the domains of smart cities (<https://tinesrail.com/>).

Kraków has taken a systemic approach to implementing Smart City solutions. In 2021, work was completed on preparing the infrastructure needed to manage the city's ICT services - mainly in terms of system integration, which facilitates the exchange of information between them.

Finalised work on the city's key reference datasets, including spatial data and data of individuals and legal entities. Applications and service systems for residents are being built on this foundation. Among the most important is the Mobile Services Platform, an application that allows services to be run on mobile devices, such as waste collection schedules, the location of sports facilities or automatic defibrillators.

In subsequent phases, it will be possible to make payments for certain municipal services. Another project is the aforementioned Portal of Electronic Services, integrated with the Internet Customer Account, which is a kind of e-window allowing one to settle official matters without leaving home.

4. Conclusion

An important element in the development of the Smart City in Krakow is the planned implementation of systems for processing large data sets based on machine learning and artificial intelligence technologies. These systems will allow advanced analysis of urban data, which will translate into very specific conclusions. This will support decision-making on Krakow's development so that it responds to the real needs of the city and its residents. This includes, for example, analysis of the city's mobility to reduce traffic jams and improve

travelling comfort, or analysis of conclusions from the aforementioned Krakow Contact Centre to optimise public services provided to residents.

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DIGIN PUBLICATIONS

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